

KNEE OSTEOARTHRITIS DETECTION USING IMAGE PROCESSING

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Abstract — *Knee osteoarthritis is the most common type of arthritis, characterized by chronic pain, crepitus, edema, morning stiffness, atrophy, decreased quadriceps muscle strength, and impaired postural control. The research on knee osteoarthritis involves observing patterns within X-ray images that are visible without the aid of magnification. The analysis of knee joint health traditionally involves labor-intensive manual examination of X-ray images, demanding specialized expertise and substantial time commitments, to overcome these challenges, the utilization of image processing techniques to automate knee osteoarthritis detection using X-ray images. By capturing X-ray images of the knee joint and comparing them against comprehensive datasets, our methodology aims to streamline the detection process, thereby reducing human error and expediting diagnosis. The data set consist of various knee X-ray images in addition to detection, users are provided with recommendations for appropriate treatments. A CNN algorithm is employed for training the knee osteoarthritis detection model.*

Keywords— *X-ray, Severity, deep learning, CNN, Tensor flow, OpenCV, Knee osteoarthritis*

I. INTRODUCTION

Knee osteoarthritis is a prevalent joint disease affecting millions worldwide, often leading to disability and reduced quality of life. early detection and appropriate intervention are pivotal in managing OA progression effectively. In this context, machine learning techniques, particularly deep learning models, offer promising avenues for accurate prediction of OA severity and personalized treatment recommendations.

Advancements in medical imaging, particularly X-ray imaging, have facilitated the diagnosis and monitoring of knee OA. X-ray images provide detailed visualization of the knee joint, allowing healthcare professionals to assess joint space narrowing, osteophyte formation, and other structural changes indicative of OA progression. Traditional medicine systems like Ayurveda offer valuable insights into the holistic management of knee OA. Ayurveda, an ancient Indian system of medicine, emphasizes the balance of bodily energies and recommends personalized approaches to health and wellness. Integrating Ayurvedic principles with modern medical practices presents a promising avenue for optimizing knee OA management. In this research paper, proposed an automated system for knee OA detection and treatment prediction using X-ray imaging and Ayurvedic principles. By leveraging machine learning algorithms and Ayurvedic knowledge, our system aims to accurately identify knee OA

severity and recommend personalized treatment strategies tailored to individual patients.

Through this interdisciplinary approach, the proposed system seeks to bridge the gap between conventional medical practices and traditional healing systems, offering a comprehensive and holistic approach to knee OA management. By leveraging both modern technology and ancient wisdom, this research aims to improve patient outcomes and quality of life for individuals living with knee Osteoarthritis.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Saini. D et al. [1] explores the use of CNNs to automate the detection and classification of knee osteoarthritis severity from X-ray images. This addresses the subjective and timeconsuming nature of manual assessment by physicians, offering a promising solution for efficient and accurate severity assessment.

Kokkotis. C et al.[2] explores the application of advanced machine learning techniques in knee osteoarthritis research. It focuses on methods such as fuzzy logic theory, discrimination metrics, and advanced classification models, along with efficient feature selection methods suitable for large datasets. The review aims to provide insights into the diverse ML methods employed in knee osteoarthritis research, including decision trees, support vector machines, neural networks, and ensemble methods like random forests or gradient boosting.

Wu .Z et al. [3] explore the application of convolutional neural networks (CNNs) in medical image analysis, particularly focusing on knee osteoarthritis severity assessment and high tibial osteotomy (HTO) procedure planning. They highlight CNNs' capability to learn complex features from images, noting their effectiveness in various applications since the breakthrough of AlexNet in image classification. The study specifically discusses techniques such as the deep Siamese CNN structure and U-Net, which have emerged as effective tools for diagnosing osteoarthritis severity and detecting brain tumors.

Woo.B et al.[4] introduces an innovative approach for automated segmentation of knee anatomical structures and the detection of bone anomalies in individuals with knee osteoarthritis. They utilize U-Net-based models for this purpose, aiming to streamline the segmentation process and improve anomaly detection accuracy in knee MR images from the Osteoarthritis Initiative.

Fatema .K.et al.[5] introduces an automated decision system for diagnosing knee osteoarthritis (KOA) by leveraging segmented X-ray images. The system utilizes optimal distance features extracted from the segmented images to facilitate accurate diagnosis. The research aims to streamline the diagnostic process for KOA using advanced image processing techniques and machine learning algorithms.

Ribas. C.L .et.al [6] focus on distinguishing between normal knee images and those indicative of minimal OA, employing the Kellgren and Lawrence classification system. This method offers a promising alternative to traditional approaches, network-based features to enhance the accuracy of early knee OA detection.

B. R. Sakar .at. el [7] explores Radiographic severity, assessed via the Kellgren-Lawrence grading scale, correlated with lower vitamin D levels in both Egyptian and Yemeni patients. Statistical analyses, including multivariate linear and logistic regression, were employed to identify independent predictors of physical function and primary KOA. The findings suggest a significant association between vitamin D deficiency and primary KOA, with implications for both disease prediction and management strategies.

M.E.Adanani at.el [8] Vibro-acoustography (VAG) has emerged as a non-invasive tool, but its accuracy is hampered by muscle-induced low-frequency irregularities during knee movement. The proposed method extracts three features from knee sounds and employs classifiers like Perceptron, MLP, SVM, GRNN, and RBF to distinguish between healthy and osteoarthritic knees. One feature demonstrates robust results with high accuracy and an F1-score, highlighting the potential for rapid, affordable, and portable knee osteoarthritis detection.

III. METHODOLOGY

The objective of this project is to develop a system for predicting knee osteoarthritis by analyzing X-ray images. The system will enable the identification of knee osteoarthritis severity and provide recommendations for treatment based on the severity level. The classification of knee osteoarthritis in the paper is done using a Flask server and a trained deep-learning model.

The algorithm used for the detection is knee **Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs)**:

For the diagnosis of knee osteoarthritis, convolutional neural networks (CNNs) stand as a powerful deep learning

approach. Recent studies demonstrate the efficacy of CNNs in accurately detecting and classifying knee osteoarthritis from X-ray images. This technique proves effective in discerning subtle structural changes indicative of knee osteoarthritis, enabling precise diagnosis and severity assessment. Developing a CNN-based knee osteoarthritis detection system involves several essential processes:

Data Gathering: To gather data for knee osteoarthritis detection, high-quality X-ray images of knees affected by osteoarthritis must be obtained and appropriately labeled. These images should be captured using high-resolution X-ray equipment to ensure clarity and detail. It is essential to meticulously label each image with the corresponding severity level of osteoarthritis, necessitating a comprehensive understanding of knee pathology. The dataset should encompass a diverse representation of patients and cover a

spectrum of severity levels to reflect the target population accurately.

Data Preprocessing: Prior to model training, preprocessing of X-ray images is imperative to enhance data quality and facilitate effective learning by the convolutional neural network (CNN) model. This preprocessing involves tasks such as noise reduction, standardization of image size, and contrast enhancement. These steps aim to mitigate inconsistencies in image quality and ensure uniformity across the dataset, thus optimizing the model's ability to extract relevant features for osteoarthritis detection. By preparing the input data meticulously, the CNN model can learn discriminative patterns indicative of knee osteoarthritis with increased accuracy and reliability.

Open CV2

OpenCV2 serves as the primary tool for image manipulation, providing functions to read, convert, and resize the X-ray images. Upon receiving the input image, OpenCV2 is employed to read the image and convert it to grayscale, simplifying subsequent processing steps. The grayscale image is then resized to the desired dimensions using OpenCV2's `resize()` function, ensuring compatibility with the CNN model's input size. Subsequently, Keras is utilized to further preprocess the resized image. The image is converted into a numpy array using Keras' `image img_to_array()` function, which facilitates its transformation into a suitable format for input into the CNN model. Additionally, Keras enables normalization of the pixel values by dividing them by 255.0, standardizing the pixel intensity values to a range between 0 and 1. This preprocessing pipeline, orchestrated by OpenCV2 and Keras, ensures that the input X-ray images are appropriately formatted and optimized for accurate severity prediction by the CNN model.

Model Training: knee X-ray images are utilized after preprocessing. These images, labeled to denote either healthy or osteoarthritic knees, serve as the training dataset for the

CNN model. As the images pass through the layers of the CNN architecture during training, the model parameters are iteratively adjusted to minimize the disparity between predicted and actual labels. Through exposure to this labeled dataset, consisting of knee X-ray images representing both healthy and osteoarthritic conditions, the model progressively learns to identify distinguishing features indicative of osteoarthritis. This iterative process enables the model to develop the ability to accurately classify knee X-ray images, effectively distinguishing between those depicting healthy knees and those exhibiting signs of osteoarthritis.

Model Validation: After the model has been trained, it is tested using a different dataset of fresh photos. This stage makes that the model is robust to generalisation and isn't overfitting the training set of data.

TensorFlow :

A popular machine learning framework called TensorFlow is frequently used to create the deep learning model, Knee osteoarthritis. TensorFlow has useful features like adjusting image contrast and reducing noise, which help in analyzing medical images. It also make the training data better by changing images slightly, like rotating or scaling them. These methods can aid in growing the training dataset's size and variety, which will boost the model's accuracy.

TensorFlow provides various pre-trained CNN models like VGG16, ResNet, and Inception, trained on extensive datasets like ImageNet. These models can serve as a base for creating knee osteoarthritis detection models using X-ray images. With smaller datasets specific to knee osteoarthritis, these pre-trained models can be fine-tuned for better performance.

TensorFlow also includes the Keras API, which is userfriendly and allows for quick prototyping of CNN models. The Keras API offers pre-built layers such as convolutional, pooling, and dense layers, making it easy to assemble a CNN model for knee osteoarthritis detection. It provides a comprehensive set of tools and features for developing accurate knee osteoarthritis detection systems using X-ray images. TensorFlow is popular among researchers and developers in the medical field due to its simplicity, adaptability, and well-documented resources. TensorFlow's rich set of features, combined with its user-friendly interface and extensive community support, makes it a preferred choice for developing advanced knee osteoarthritis diagnostic systems using X-ray images.

1.Importing Libraries needed for detecting the Knee osteoarthritis

```
app.py > load_my_model
1 from flask import Flask, render_template, request
2 from keras.models import load_model
3 from tensorflow.keras.preprocessing import image
4 import numpy as np
5 import cv2
```

2.Loads the model using the following code with

```
tf.keras.utils.custom_object_scope(custom_disease):
```

```
model = load_model('model.h5')
```

Here we loads the pre-trained Keras model from a saved file (model.h5) using the load_model() function from tf.keras. The custom_object_scope function allows to register any custom objects required by the model, so that the model can be correctly deserialized.

The algorithm used in this system is Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) that provides greater accuracy.

Predicting the knee osteoarthritis using the following code:

```
@app.route("/predict", methods=['GET', 'POST'])
def upload():
    if request.method == 'POST':
        img = request.files['file']
        img_path = "uploads/" + img.filename
        img.save(img_path)
        severity = predict_label(img_path)
        treatment_plan = predict_treatment(severity)
        # Calculate accuracy for the predicted severity
        accuracy = calculate_accuracy(severity)
        # Return the severity, treatment plan, and accuracy separately
        response = f"Predicted Severity: {severity}\nTreatment Plan: {treatment_plan}\nAccuracy: {accuracy}"
        return response
```

The Flask application has an endpoint /predict that expects a POST request with a JSON payload containing a base64encoded image.Using OpenCV's imdecode function, the bytes are converted into a numpy array representing the image. The pre-trained model is used to make predictions on the image using the predict() function, which returns an

array of probabilities for each class. The predicted label is obtained by finding the index of the maximum probability using the `argmax()` method

IV RESULT

Based on the dataset provided, application enables the detection of knee osteoarthritis by analyzing X-ray images. Users upload an X-ray image of the affected knee and initiate the prediction process by clicking the predict button. The system then analyzes the uploaded image to identify the severity of knee osteoarthritis and offers a description of the condition, along with recommended treatment plans. First we have to upload the xray image of the knee which is affected by the disease and press the predict button as shown in figure 1

figure 1

When the predict button is clicked the input image will be checked with the trained data and if there is any matching and the most matching profile will be printed as the output as shown in figure 2

figure 2

V CONCLUSION

The paper provides a method to knee osteoarthritis detection using Convolutional Neural Network. Here primarily we teach the system various severity that may occur to the x-ray. The dataset contains various class of severity. When the input image is uploaded the image is compared with the dataset and the most accurate result will be provided. The most matching result will be considered as the output with a short description treatment plan. The system is very helpful for automated disease detection.

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